

Secure Reversible Image Steganography Over Encrypted Domain Using Public Key

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Abstract—Hiding information in an image in a way that does not affect the original cover image pixels or cause a permanent distortion after extracting that information is known as reversible data hiding technology. Many reversible data hiding schemes have been proposed and successfully applied in military applications. Such schemes are developed to ensure digital images' authenticity and integrity without any distortion of the original images. They guarantee that any attempt to change the watermarked image will be detected by the image owner. In this research, an algorithm is proposed to reversibly hide data into encrypted grayscale images in a separable manner. The proposed work exploits only LSB insertion for steganography. Scope exists for adopting frequency domain manipulation which may further improve the security of the signal. Comparison with the state-of-the-art methods; the proposed approach provides higher embedding capacity and can perfectly reconstruct the original image as well as the embedded message. Extensive experimental results are provided to validate the superior performance of our scheme.

Keywords— Data Hiding, Steganography, Reversible Data Hiding, Image Processing, Images Authenticity Embedded Message

I. INTRODUCTION

Preserving information safe while conveying it to someone at a distance has been on people's minds since the dawn of time, leading to the development of very basic to extremely specific computer-based approaches. Around the last four to five decades, there has been a massive exchange of data all over the world. The internet and the computer network's remarkable growth spawned and simplified a plethora of E-Commerce apps. This seeks assurance of data security and any potential misuse resulting from the loss of information. Individual communication becomes more important as

ultimate confidentiality becomes a demand. As a result, there is a requirement for data transfer in encoded or modified form.

In multimedia communication, privacy and authenticity become even more important, especially when computer networks like the internet are open and vulnerable. In today's world of worldwide connectedness, intruders, hackers, computer viruses, eavesdropping, digital fraud, and cybercrime fraud, it's critical to protect vital information from falling into the wrong hands. Cryptography is the study that deals with the process of secreted writing in which original information is encoded into an incoherent form that can't be decoded by an adversary, whereas steganography hides the secret information in other mediums and thus can't be seen. The data in ciphertext may raise suspicions in the interceptor's mind, but a steganographically hidden message is ignored.

Cryptography, Steganography, and Watermarking are three interconnected techniques that have been discovered in the literature. Cryptography is a different branch from steganography and watermarking, which both belong to the class of information concealment and are quite comparable.

The possible cover carriers in steganography are innocent-looking carriers that will store the hidden information (images, music, video, text, or some other digitally represented code). The information hidden is called a message, and it can be plaintext, ciphertext, pictures, or anything else that can be encoded in a bitstream. A stego-carrier is made of the cover carrier and the embedded message. Hiding data may necessitate the use of a stego-key, which is additional secret data, such as a password, required for embedding the data. A possible formula of the process may be represented as:

Cover medium + embedded message + stego key = stego-medium

Figure 1: Graphical Version of the Steganographic System

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fE: steganographic function "embedding"
fE-1: steganographic function "extracting"
cover: cover data in which emb will be hidden
emb: message to be hidden
stego: cover data with the hidden message

The benefit of steganography is that it may be used to send messages invisibly without the transmission being detected. Encryption can often be used to identify the sender or receiver as someone who has something to hide. The image of our cat, for example, may hide the plans for our company's next technological innovation.

The necessity for a high level of security for personnel communication and legal authenticity (authentication for commercial purposes) necessitates the use of innovative and effective solutions. Cryptography and Steganography, respectively, are time-tested and well-developed techniques for hiding data by scrambling it to make it unintelligible or hiding it in a cover media. These strategies have been well-developed for sending data across insecure transmission channels. They provide enough protection, but they are insufficient for the current information era or digital needs.

So, to meet the needs of the day, the goal of this work is to conduct a thorough analysis of existing Cryptographic and Steganographic algorithms, as well as the current technique for picture encryption and embedding mechanism, to suggest a fresh strategy for improving security. The following are the research's key goals:

1. Study of existing Cryptographic techniques find their advantages and shortcoming.
2. Study of existing Steganographic techniques find its advantages and shortcoming.
3. Develop a technique or system (a new approach), possibly by combining two above said techniques i.e., Cryptography and Steganography.
4. The objective is to develop a more reliable, secure, and trusted means of communication.

II. RELATED WORK

Kordov K. et. al. (2021), Combining steganography and encryption, a method for hiding secret text messages in color graphics is provided. Using a chaotic pseudorandom generator, the location and order of the image pixels chosen for information embedding are picked at random. Another layer of security is to encrypt the secret message before embedding it to deceive attackers who are looking for steganography traces. The proposed stego algorithm is being evaluated. Randomness testing, key-space analysis, key-sensitivity analysis, visual analysis, histogram analysis, peak

signal-to-noise ratio analysis, chi-square analysis, and other common statistical and empirical tests are utilized. In this article, the collected results are given and explained.

G. Mallikharjuna Rao (2020), A combination of encryption and image steganography techniques is offered. This approach will ensure security by preventing the extraction of the secret message and image. The functionality is based on the International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA) cryptographic techniques and the Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) based steganography algorithm. The document is encrypted and decrypted using cryptography. For the secure transfer of secret data through the internet, steganography is used to disguise a document inside an image with an increased payload. We describe a single application in this paper to disguise the sender's information, which is so important and secret in the form of files that it will be invisible to unauthorized people. The results of a proposed technique with a payload of 52,400 bytes of information in an image and a PSNR of 90.06 dB.

Jemima Dias et. al. (2020), suggested study entails a picture encryption algorithm that employs a secret key derived from the Lorenz chaotic system. It's a weighted network that XORs the plain picture's Y channel and produces the cipher image. These weights are one-of-a-kind and not interchangeable. The decoded plain image has a similarity index of 0.96 to the original plain image, according to the results.

Serdar Solak et. al. (2019) To hide encrypted data in the cover picture, presented adaptive least-significant-bit (LSB)+3 type I and adaptive LSB+3 type II approaches. The suggested adaptive LSB+3 method produces a stego image with higher image quality than typical three-bit LSB methods. A peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) better than 41 dB is achieved when maximal data is incorporated in the cover image. Adaptive LSB+3 type I and adaptive LSB+3 type II approaches have better PSNR values (3.48 percent and 5.73 percent, respectively) than regular three-bit LSB replacement methods, according to experiments.

Swati Bhargava et. al. (2019) The suggested image encryption is accomplished by LSB bits, DWT, and the RSA method. This research also discusses novel ways that use encryption and steganography to jumble data and cover the insights in other media using picture processing (IP). The encrypted image can be hidden in another image using LSB bits and DWT methods, allowing the secret message to be discovered. Because the secret material has been encrypted by the recipient's public key, the receiver will utilize his/her private key. By using DWT, you can hide an encrypted image in the cover image. DWT decrypts text and extracts encrypted images from the cover image. The proposed technique is built using recommended cryptography and steganography regulations on the MATLAB platform. PSNR and MSE should be calculated. Calculate the entropy of the cover and stego images as well.

Amit Khare et. al. (2018), The OUTGUESS algorithm was proposed. One of the embedding algorithms that embed messages in the DCT domain is outguessed. Outguess divides the embedding procedure into two stages. It first finds the redundant DCT, then chooses bits in which to incorporate the message based on the information gathered in the first phase. The Digital Image Steganography system is a stand-alone application that combines steganography and encryption to increase the message's confidentiality. To create unreadable ciphertext, the user's intended message is first encrypted. The encrypted text will then be buried within a picture file in such a way that the observed loss in quality is minimized. With the help of the Digital Image Steganography system, the recipient of the image can recover the concealed message.

Mohammed Mahdi Hashim et. al. (2018), The goal of this research is to improve the imperceptibility of a proposed approach with a large secret message payload capacity. The suggested technique employs two key processes: embedding and extracting. Before the embedding procedure, the secret message is compressed using the Huffman coding technique. After preparing a secret message, the proposed method's security and capacity will improve. The suggested scheme's main goal is to improve image quality (PSNR) in stego images. The method's effectiveness is due to two key factors: first, testing secret bit matching with LSB and mapping to detect even and odd words during embedding, and second, segmenting the secret message to track and map every bit in the stego picture. The suggested method's experimental results show that it can attain a high level of imperceptibility and robustness.

Kamaldeep Joshi et. al. (2018), suggested that conceals information along a given pixel and on the next value of that pixel, pixel + 1. The selected pixel has one bit concealed, while the pixel +1 value has a second bit hidden. Based on the 7th bit of an image's pixels, a mathematical function is applied to the 7th bit of the pixels, resulting in the generation of a temporary variable (pixel + 1). Information is hidden and extracted using the 7th bit of the selected pixel and the 7th bit of pixel + 1. Two bits of the message can be buried on each pixel using a combination of these two values. Following implementation, the method's efficiency is assessed using parameters such as PSNR and MSE, and a comparison with several previously proposed algorithms is made.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Cryptographic techniques are mainly applied to the text message and are secure. However rare attempt has been made to encrypt images. The Steganography is rather very simple are predictable and thus not very secure. The techniques are being used primarily for hiding data.

A rare attempt has been used to combine the two and make steganography more secure for images using cryptography.

Few attempts have been made combining the two techniques by employing cryptographic techniques on the text and embedding messages into a cover image using steganography but so far, no attempts have been made to combine these techniques and pre-process the secrete image i.e. encryption of image before embedding into the cover image. The developed system will provide an enhanced level of security of data across unsafe communication channels.

To attain the better of the two techniques, a combination of the two has also been tried. However, they remain susceptible to attacks and could be breached with the knowledge of algorithms and little luck. This leads to the motivation for further improving the existing techniques so that a real-time implementation algorithm can be developed which is safe from attacks and vulnerability.

Given the strength of Cryptography and Steganography, an improved safe secured system is suggested. This proposed system concatenates cryptography and steganography techniques to give high security, more robust, and higher payload. The suggested technique comprising of four main steps as illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Structure of Proposed Model

1. Encoding Function
2. Embedding Function
3. Retrieval Function
4. Decoding Function

A. Encoding Function using AES

Initially, the secrete image is chosen for the encoding function. The intensity value of every pixel of the secrete image is transformed from a decimal to a binary value. By taking Thirty-two successive pixels one block of 256-bits is formed. This constructed block is now inputted to the AES encoding function [3]. The complete process is described as below:

The proposed method used a 256-bits version allowing 256-bits block size and 256-bits key size. Advance Encryption Standard comprising of four fundamental operational blocks. These operations are performed on an array of words/ bytes and organized as a 4x4 matrix called state. Data are processed in 10 rounds for one entire encryption. Every round controls the following transformation.

1. Bytesub Transformation: This transformation function substitutes the byte by using the S-Box mapping table [50, 52]. This table is formulated by affine transformation and multiplicative inverse function. Byte Substitution controls each byte of state individually, with the input byte being used to index a row and column in the lookup table to generate the substitute value.

2. Shiftrows Transformation: This transformation is again an easy byte transformation function. The values of the last three rows of state are circularly shifted. The left shifting of a byte are differ by one to three-byte in each row.

3. Mixcolumns Transformations: The mix columns transformation works on each column autonomously. Every byte of a column is replaced by new bytes which are dependent on all four bytes carrying current value in that column using special function arithmetic over GF(28). This mapping function is based on matrix multiplication in which all resultant values are dependent on all values in that column. The difference is only that the byte is treated as a polynomial in GF (28). In the decryption module, the inverse mapping function with different settings on constants is used. The output of this transformation is perfect mixing of bytes in the same column. The mixing of columns offers a proper avalanche effect in the minimum round because all output bytes are strongly dependant on every input byte.

4. Addroundkey Transformation: As the title told AddRoundKey Transformation is simple XORing among the round key and current working state. This function is self-reversible.

5. AES Key Expansion: The key expansion algorithm

provides one 16-byte key for the initial AddRoundKey stage and ten sub-keys for every 10 rounds of encryption. This algorithm starts with taking input of 4 words (16 Byte) initial key and copying the initial key into the group of four words. Subsequently constructing the next four group based on the previous four-word are performed. The first byte in every group is specially treated by rotate + S-box + XOR function with previous work before XORing the one from four back.

The Value of the initial 32 pixels of the secrete image is converted into 32 pixels of the encrypted secret image after absolute execution of the AES encryption module. This encoded image offers an adequate level of safety during transmission on the unsafe communication channels.

B. Embedding Function

Now for bit division for embedding function, the encrypted secrete image is taken. The pixel value of the image is transferred from decimal to binary. Assume that the value of the first pixel of the encrypted image is:

$$[(173)]_{10} = (10101101)_2$$

The received 8 bits binary pixel value is divided into four equal parts of 2 bits.

Figure 3: Bit Division for Insertion

b1 = 10, b2 = 10, b3 = 11, b4 = 01 receive after bit division procedure.

1. Insertion of Bit into the Cover Image: The received values of b1, b2, b3, b4 are now inserted into a cover image using the LSB embedding method. Now takes four successive pixels from the cover image and 2 LSB bits of each pixel are replaced by b1, b2, b3, and b4 systematically.

2. Formation of Stego Image: After the insertion of bits into a pixel of the cover image, the modified pixel values are received. The modified values are placed into the original position. Similarly, by one-pixel value from the secrete image is taken and embedded into this value into the next four consecutive pixels of the cover image. The modified value of cover image pixels is put into the original location. After processing the whole secrete image, a stego image is formed which hides secrete image.

Encoding & Embedding Algorithm

Input: Gray level Secrete Image (m × n), A gray Level Cover of size (2m × 2n);

Output: Stego Image of size (2m × 2n);

Steps:

1. Value of 32 pixels of the secret image form block of 256-bits. This is inputted to the image encoding Function (AES), which produces the encrypted secret image.
2. Divide each pixel value of encrypted secret image into 4 parts each containing 2 bits each.
3. Insert these 2-bit pixel values into the LSB position of the first four pixels in the cover image one by one.
4. End.

C. Image Retrieval Function

Decoding of the stego image is executed at the receiver end. The process of decoding is described below:

1. Generate the 2 LSB Bits from the Stego Image

The Pixel value from the stego image is taken one by one and processed these pixels. The pixel value is converted into binary representation and extracts 2 LSB's bits from four successive pixels of the stego image. The value of the first pixel is 110, convert it into binary sequence 01101110 received. Extracting 2 LSB's from this sequence, a value of b1 is found.

Accordingly taking next three-pixel values i.e., 242, 35, 97;

$$(242)_{10} = (11110010)_2$$

$$(35)_{10} = (00100011)_2$$

$$(97)_{10} = (01100001)_2$$

Giving the value of

$$b1 = 10; b2 = 10; b3 = 11; b4 = 01$$

2. Concatenation of Results: The output of four two bits values i.e., b1, b2, b3 and b4 are concatenated to produce single 8- bits binary value. This value is the value of first pixel of encrypted secret image.

Figure 5: Formation of Stego Image

3. Formation of Encrypted Secret Image: The received value of the first pixel is placed at the first position in reconstructing the image. Similarly, the next four pixels are selected again and repeat the whole retrieval module which gives the next pixel value of the reconstructed image. The complete encrypted secret image is reconstructed in this way by the processing of the complete stego image.

D. Decoding Function using AES

1. Formation of Secret Image: To recover the secret image from the encrypted secret image, the AES decoding module is executed. Now the encrypted secret image is selected and a value of 32 successive pixels is taken. On concatenation of these values, a block of 256-bits is formed. This block is inputted to the AES decoding function in which secret keys are used in reverse sequence. The output of 256-bits is split into 32 parts, which gives the value of 32 respective pixels in the secret image. In the same way, the whole secret image is retrieved.

Decoding Algorithm

Input: Stego Image of size $(2m \times 2n)$;

Output: A grey level Secret Image $(m \times n)$;

Steps:

1. Input each pixel and take 2-bit LSB from 4 consecutive pixel values of the stego image.
2. Concatenate four 2-bit LSB to obtain 8 bits of each pixel value of the encrypted secret image.
3. Now 32 consecutive pixel values forming a block of 256-bits are inputted to decoding Function (AES) using the same parameter but keys value used in reverse order, to get the first eight-pixel value of the secret image.
4. End.

The proposed steganographic system improves the safety level and quality of the image as compared to the existing conventional steganographic system by using the S-box mapping function and secret key. Earlier cryptographic systems are having their weakness and are easily

compromised or by contemporaneous computational power. AES algorithm efficiently works on software and hardware, the execution of AES is quick even on small computing devices like smartphones, smart card devices, tabs, etc. A larger block size with multiple size keys (128,192 and 256-bits) provides additional security. AES is versatile and can employ on any size of data using multi-choice key length. According to NIST, AES is the replacement of 3DES and it will work safely and cope with technological development up to the year 2030.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

The algorithms or proposed methods were verified on three dissimilar standard images set namely Leena, moon, and ship. They have been taken as sample cases depicting three sets of characteristics of images.

1. Lena on the other hand has pixel well spread over midrange components with no low and very high pixel values.
2. The moon image has lots of low-value components with narrow midrange pixels.
3. Ship image is highly biased towards high frequency in the extreme band with practically large zero bands at the lower.

Figure 6: shows the three Leena. png image1; a) image is the original image; b) encrypted image and c) stego image

Figure 7: shows the stego image and original image after decryption for the leena.png image

Figure 8: shows the three moon.png image2; a) image is the original image; b) encrypted image and c) stego image

Figure 9: shows the stego image and original image after decryption for the moon.png image

Figure 10: shows the three ship.png image3; a) image is the original image; b) encrypted image and c) Stego image

Figure 11: shows the stego image and original image after

decryption for the ship.png image

A. Comparative Analysis

Table 1: Embedding Performance Comparison of Proposed System

Image Name	Image Size	admin	Entropy	Standard Deviation
Leena	512 * 512	4	1.4072e04	3.2186
Moon	512 * 512	4	6.5303e03	0
Ship	512 * 512	4	5.4331e03	28.1718
Parrot	512 * 512	4	6.1024e03	0.8655

Accuracy

we tabulate the embedding capacity and data extraction accuracy α of our method [13], [14] for different settings of block size. Here, τ is defined by

$$\alpha = \frac{\text{No. of correctly extracted bits}}{\text{No. of embedded bits}}$$

and the values given are averaged over all the blocks in the 5 test images. Our method can embed 21675 message bits for each 512x512 image when the block size is 8x8 while ensuring 98% accuracy of data extraction. As the block size decreases further, a small number of extraction errors appear. our method is significantly higher than those of [13] and [14], while the embedding capacity is three times higher.

In addition to the comparison of the averaged extraction accuracy, we also show the results for four representative images shown in graph 1.

Table 2: Comparison of the extraction accuracy for Single test images (Leena)

Image Name	Block Size	Ref [13]	Ref [14]	Proposed (%)
Leena	8 * 8	89.4468%	92.0461%	98.976%
	8 * 7	88.4133%	91.4372%	98.865%
	7 * 7	87.2088%	90.6550%	98.541%
	7 * 6	85.7437%	89.6938%	98.216%

Graph 1: Comparative analysis of extraction accuracy of the

proposed method with existing methods for Single test images (Leena)

Table 3: Comparison of the embedding capacity for a single test image (Leena).

Image Name	Block Size	Ref [13]	Ref [14]	Proposed (%)
Leena	8 * 8	4096 bits	4096 bits	12288 bits
	8 * 7	4672 bits	4672 bits	14016 bits
	7 * 7	5329 bits	5329 bits	15987 bits
	7 * 6	6205 bits	6205 bits	18615 bits

In Table 3, we fix $n = 3$ in our method, i.e., each block accommodates 3 bits. As the scheme of [13] only works on blocks no less than 3×3 , the results for smaller block configurations are marked with - For a fair comparison with [13] and [14], we try different numbers of flipped LSBs, instead of fixing to flip three LSBs and only record the best extraction accuracy in Table 5.3. This is equivalent to removing the constraint on direct decryption. It can be observed that, for all three methods, the embedding capacity increases as the block size drops.

CONCLUSION

The model of merging cryptographic and steganographic systems to achieve additional secure and robust data is employed. As a precursor, pre-processing is sustained to enhance security features. The secret image to be transmitted is encrypted using well-known encryption algorithms. The encrypted image is then hidden into a cover image using steganographic techniques.

The pre-processing encrypts the secret image before being used as an input to be inserted into the cover image maintaining the eminence of the stego image as near as undistorted. The encryption of the image is accomplished by the well-proven text encryption scheme, AES algorithms. This ensures that even if the steganographic technique fails and attacks to counter the embedding are employed, the extracted image is still in the encrypted shape.

The proposed work is exploited only LSB insertion for steganography. Scope exists for adopting frequency domain manipulation which may further improve the security of the signal.

We compare with the state-of-the-art methods; the proposed approach provides higher embedding capacity and can perfectly reconstruct the original image as well as the embedded message. Extensive experimental results are provided to validate the superior performance of our scheme.

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